

Love and Education Beyond the Event Horizon: An Apology to Christopher Nolan

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Introduction

This paper engages with the concept of love in education through an analysis of the motion picture *Interstellar* by Christopher Nolan. Love is taken as a necessarily tricky, elusive, concept—taking for granted that anything that appears simple and predictable might be some kind of love-like thing, but not the kind of love that is of interest here. The love of interest here is a kind of gravity-shattering force that releases the sciences from their epistemological event horizons. It's love, but not as 'we' know it (the 'we' here referring to any culture that has typically disregarded or marginalised love in some way).

Interstellar adds some complexity to working philosophically with love in education through its association of love with event horizons—the film takes up something of a logic and a science of love to suggest that love is both an essential condition and a provocation for thinking through the seemingly impossible equations that confound the physical sciences. Those associations are explored through the flows of the narrative, and observations of a selection of key characters.

The application of Nolan's work on love is speculative, presenting a sense of the ways in which science fiction might offer the philosophy of education different tools to tinker with the things that matter. "Science fiction, in our reading of it, does not need to stand up to science in order to be effective ... it gives us license to engage in a series of aesthetic thought experiments, of what currently is and where it might go" (Gibbons and Kupferman, 2019, pp. 168-169). In this paper, that tinkering is explored as resonant with the work of Heidegger and Camus. Both writers are read here as offering a way into science fiction as poetic work in the philosophy of education. Their respective questions with regard science lend a hand to the task of questioning science and education through science fiction.

In the study of education, science fiction is educational in its engagement with speculation on the what ifs and the why nots: speculations that are not simply future focused, but rather are approaches to imagining the already present. For example, first contact with a galaxy travelling civilisation is not limited to thinking ahead, it is also productive for thinking back (the abiding narratives that generate thoughts about colonisation) and the present (the ways in which a society or community might not notice that which is already at hand). Science fiction

demands something of the imagination, in a way that sparks a wonder. Here wonder is more than simply a curiosity about the future; wonder generates both present and future in its existentially generative sense..... [W]ithin this concept of wonder, kept at arm's length from the cold calculations and measurements of an analytic mind, is a more radical imagination of new questions, and an intensification of these questions

concerning being in the present. (Gibbons and Kupferman, 2019, p 170)

Using science fiction to explore love and education adds to existing scholarly engagement on, for just a few examples, love and pedagogy (Goldstein, 1997; Page, 2018), love and the purpose of education (Lin, 2006), love and child rearing (de Grice, Braun, and Wetherell, 2017), love and community (Cram, 2021) and love and critical education (Lanas and Zembylas, 2015).

When using cinema, science fiction or otherwise, to engage with the philosophy of education, it's perhaps important to first make disclaimers and alerts. A disclaimer: this is not a cinematic review of the film within the field of cinematic studies. While the work here may add to cinematic studies, that is not its purpose. An alert: If the reader has not seen *Interstellar* then this article is full of spoilers. I recommend putting the paper down and watching the film. However, I also recognise that reading about a film and watching that same film can happen in any order with generative implications, particularly if being conditioned and warned as to (an interpretation of) the film's devices is not a problem.

In this paper, the thinking that is nurtured through an exploration of *Interstellar* is then applied to education policy and curriculum through two contexts: 1) epistemological debates concerning scientific and “Indigenous knowledge” (Stewart, 2021a, p. 2) systems in one bicultural nation; and 2) early childhood care and education as a distinct and problematic education ‘sector’ in many nations. Early childhood education and care is of interest here because of its nearness to the problem of love in education and because of the direct reference to love through the concept of *aroha* in *Mātauranga Māori*—a reference that symbolises a persistent tension for curriculum and policy writers, and for the children and adults who come together to form early childhood care and education communities.

Interstellar

The central characters in *Interstellar* are Coop and Murph—father and daughter. Other characters of interest include the black hole Gargantua, the robot TARS and the astronaut scientists Mann and Brand.

When we meet the Coopers, Murph is talking about a ghost in her room. She's not scared of the ghost; rather, she thinks it's trying to communicate with her. Coop argues that suggesting there's a ghost trying to communicate with her is not very scientific. Murph replies to Coop, “you said science is about admitting what we don't know.” Coop then encourages Murph to start observing the phenomenon, gathering all the facts. Coop is especially proud of Murph and her love of science, so inviting her to gather all the facts is not undermining or dismissing a daughter, but rather a celebration of knowing a daughter—he loves Murph, and knows what makes Murph tick.

This love for Murph plays out in a scene at school. Coop is brought in to talk to the principal and to Murph's teacher about Murph's behaviour. Murph has been fighting, which is concerning. But more concerning for the teacher is that Murph is fighting about a disagreement over a book of Coop's that she brought to school. The book speaks of a history in which an organisation called NASA chose to go to the moon. As such, this book is banned at school for spreading misinformation about the space race of the mid-twentieth century. The moon landing never

happened. Murph's teacher explains with certainty that the moon landing was a conspiracy.

In *Interstellar*, a teacher can genuinely, and with an unquestioning faith, state the moon landing was a cunning fiction designed to undermine the Soviet Union during the Cold War—convincing the Soviet Union to invest in a mythical space race gives the United States some breathing space. Those that talked of conspiracies to manufacture the moon landing were right—it was a conspiracy. Anyone who now suggests that NASA did actually land on the moon is the new conspiracy theorist undermining humanity's mission to save a dying planet. Conveniently then, it is organisations like NASA that can be shown to be responsible for the predicament of the planet (Peters et al., 2021). In *Interstellar*, a good teacher and a good curriculum is concerned with a rationality that allows for the greatest number to survive without further environmental degradation. But the clock is ticking, and no one seems to seriously think there's any possibility of saving the planet.

Coop is unwilling to believe that there is no future. He is ex-NASA and believes that living the best life involves looking up to the stars and believing in an extra-terrestrial future for humanity. So, Coop is also unwilling to discipline Murph for her behaviour at school. The teacher and principal are mocked by Coop, who advises them he is going to punish Murph by treating her to a baseball game.

Murph, meanwhile, is happily gathering data on a phenomenon with a thorough and rational belief that something is trying to communicate with her, and that her father and brother are playfully dismissing it as a ghost. Coop's failure to believe in an entity trying to communicate with Murph is ironic, because it's actually him attempting to communicate with himself through Murph. And paradoxically, if he is successful in the future at stopping himself in the past, he never ends up in that future, at least as far as we can make sense of time at the moment. Present Coop is failing to listen to future Coop in warning present Coop to stay on Earth and not fly through a mysterious wormhole leading to a new and potentially habitable galaxy of planets.

When Coop realises that there is indeed something communicating with Murph, and that it is communicating in binary, he discovers the coordinates to a secret NASA base where NASA is working on an equation that will enable an exodus from the dying Earth. Solving the problem of gravity appears unlikely, so, at the same time, NASA is sending human embryos through a wormhole that has been deposited near Saturn and appears to be a benign intervention aimed at opening access to habitable planets in another galaxy.

Having not heeded his own future warning to himself, Coop travels through the wormhole and ends up in a system of three potentially habitable planets orbiting a black hole that NASA has decided to call Gargantua. Gargantua is explained as a collapsed star. Nothing escapes Gargantua's event horizon, not even light, although this debated astrophysical theory (see Curiel, 2019) regarding the inescapability of events beyond the event horizon turns out to be incorrect. All the same, NASA plans to send in a probe to gather data, believing that somewhere beyond this inescapable event horizon is an answer, and that maybe for a brief moment some data can be relayed out of the black hole by the probe.

Gargantua has a huge gravitational pull, and the closer that the expedition flies to it, the more their

experience of time slows down compared to Earth. The team has to decide just how much time they can lose and return to an Earth still habited by their loved ones. In arguing over which habitable planet to head to in this new galaxy, Brand, who happens to be in love with one of the three astronauts alone on one of the three potentially habitable planets, argues that following one's heart could be a legitimate approach to solving the problem of which direction to take. Brand argues that "we've spent too long trying to figure [time and gravity] out with theory." She goes on: "Love isn't something we invented, it's observable, powerful. It has to have meaning." Love, Brand argues, "is the one thing that we're capable of perceiving that transcends time and space." Love might bust through the apparently impervious event horizon, and so events become newly available from beyond the horizon.

Gargantua is a key character in *Interstellar*, offering an event horizon past, or perhaps through, which humanity hopes it might find paradigm-changing formulae—answers to questions that have yet to be asked. For the science of *Interstellar*, Gargantua offers challenges to experiences of time and gravity, and their association with yet to be discovered dimensions (Davis, 2021). Nolan worked with astrophysicists in creating Gargantua, in order to "attempt depicting a black hole as it would actually be seen by somebody nearby" (James et al., 2015, p. 1). The aim was to "make the film as scientifically accurate as possible—within constraints of not confusing his mass audience unduly and using images that are exciting and fresh" (James et al., 2015, p. 22). Gargantua, then, in a sense, invites us to wonder whether there's something beyond the horizons of science within the black hole—and who is to say that whatever that something unimaginable is, that it might not be love? Coop, driven by a concern to return to earth with a minimal loss of years, disregards Brand's appeal to a new theory of love, and they head off to Dr. Mann's planet.

The leader of a previous expedition through the wormhole, Dr. Mann is considered a hero because he committed to a mission which had little chance of success and most likely would result in him dying alone on an uninhabitable planet. It was a one-way trip unless the planet was habitable. Dr. Mann has a change of heart. He decides he does not want to sacrifice his life for humanity when he realises the planet is uninhabitable, and he tricks Coop and the rest of the team in order to escape the planet and save himself. Mann apologises to Coop as he smashes Coop's space suit and leaves Coop to die on the planet. Mann's apology takes the form of an ironic lecture on how the imagination of loved ones will be the last thing Coop thinks of. Mann explains that this connection to loved ones is humanity's greatest source of inspiration—the human survival instinct is powered by intimacy. That intimacy, Dr. Mann argues, "rarely extends beyond our line of sight." Mann theorises love as an evolutionary function. He ascribes a scientific rationale for love in this sense; however, it's limited to survival in the face of adversity. Love conjures up loved ones to generate a little more desire to stay alive.

Coop manages to survive Dr. Mann's attack on his spacesuit, chases after Dr. Mann, and Dr. Mann then dies attempting to steal Coop's ship in a bid to return to a dying Earth.

Then, and this is important, Coop sacrifices himself for the mission, propelling Brand to the final possible habitable planet, exhausting his own fuel and getting sucked into Gargantua. This is where we find out that

- a) There is indeed dimension-changing data to see once inside the black hole, beyond the event horizon
- b) You can escape a black hole

In *Gargantua*, Coop finds himself in a visual and physical representation of Murph's room back on Earth, a representation which he can alter. It's now that Coop realises it was him sending messages to Murph, including the coordinates for NASA and the warning to stay on Earth. He also realises that Brand was right—that there is a quantifiable love between father and daughter that enables a power of connection that transcends time and space. Coop realises that this representation of Murph's room, and the wormhole itself, are not gifts from a benign intergalactic Santa Claus, but rather an access key and blueprint from his own human future. With the help of the robot TARS, Coop uses this connection to transmit the secrets of *Gargantua* as data to Murph, data which enables Murph to complete the necessary equations for escaping the gravity of Earth.

Coop achieves the seemingly impossible. He crosses a conceptual threshold and discovers a new truth to the appearance of the event horizon. *Gargantua* sucks him beyond the horizon. The love that matters here is the love that confounds Dr. Mann. Coop submits himself to the gravity of *Gargantua* and gets pulled into the black hole, accepting that he will not escape, he will not see Murph again. There are some complex love equations to explore here. Love reveals a connection that transcends time and space, and love reveals a capacity to throw oneself into an apparent void.

The apology: Love, science and philosophy

This paper is developed as an apology because I was initially critical and dismissive of the positioning of love as a *deus ex machina* described above. Perhaps not as much as TV science and technology personality Adam Savage (2014), who shared in a review of the film, "I was not moved by the plot, even a little bit ... the plot of *Interstellar* left me cold cold cold and I was very sad about that." One might argue that being left feeling cold is a kind of movement that is worth exploring. I too felt a little cold, hostile to the use of love to solve the necessary equations and resolve the problem of escaping a poorly (if at all) loved Earth. This device seemed to be cheap.

Over time, this analysis appeared more than just unnecessarily hostile; it failed to see nuance in Brand's hypothesis and in Coop's experiment. Here I want to challenge that it is important to explore what Brand might offer when she argues that "we've spent too long trying to figure [time and gravity] out with theory," to recognise persistent challenges to what counts as science, and to speculate on some alternative ways of thinking through the themes of love and science in the philosophy of education.

Brand needn't think of love as some kind of theory vacuum. Recognising that love "isn't something we invented, it's observable, powerful" is entirely theoretical. What Brand might be taken to mean to say is that there's been a tendency to look behind only some select bushes (Nietzsche, 1979) for the right scientific theories. Brand challenges that it is time to look behind bushes that have been disregarded for their relevance to seemingly proper questions concerning science.

Brand is asking that her colleagues reconceptualise what is and what is not scientific. This is a

debate of significance in Aotearoa New Zealand, with particular concern for the ways in which claims to what counts as scientific legitimacy has led to a recognition of the ways in which epistemological chauvinisms (Young, 2002) continue to operate in a supposedly bicultural nation that is bonded in partnership by a treaty which acknowledges the knowledge rights of the treaty partners.

As the nation explores more deeply and broadly what such a partnership might mean for bicultural epistemologies, a hostility has amplified with regard to cultural knowledge, with claims from within the academic science community that cultural knowledge is of cultural importance for cultures, but cannot make claims to being scientific knowledge (see Stewart, 2021a). In this debate, the public of Aotearoa New Zealand has been served a “warning that science is being attacked by Mātauranga Māori” (Stewart, 2021a, p. 1). In exploring the political and philosophical dimensions of this debate, Stewart explains, “traditional Māori cosmogenic and nature narratives taken together make up the paradigm and philosophy of mātauranga, within which Māori empirical knowledge is organised and makes sense” (Stewart, 2022, p. 22).

Stewart counters concerns with regard to any apparent undermining of science with the challenge that “the boundary between science and Indigenous knowledge has historically helped science to define itself” (Stewart, 2021a, p. 2), hence challenging the grounds upon which any warning to the public might be made. At the same time, Stewart (2022) offers a challenge to any attempts to see science and Mātauranga Māori as commensurate with particular attention to the observation that there’s little agreement on what counts as science (Stewart, 2022). Stewart (2022, p. 19) argues:

All cultural knowledges or ethnosciences involve knowledge of nature, collect evidence using the human senses, and use logical thinking to process experience and guide decision-making. In this sense, mātauranga counts as a science. But such general descriptors do not justify the claim that all cultural knowledge bases are therefore “the same” as contemporary science knowledge. (Stewart, 2022, p. 20)

Brand’s problem is then one which might open her up to the colonising tendencies of a science that she has long been dedicated to, but for which she had lacked the philosophical imagination to see beyond.

A key challenge for Brand is to avoid any theory of the transcendence of love being assimilated into a narrowed understanding of what counts as science. This is an essential concern with a significant history and contemporary relevance for knowledge. Stewart (2022, p. 21) suggests that

To examine the relationship between mātauranga and science shines a light on the “invisible” philosophy of science. In this sense, mātauranga acts as a mirror for science: a way for Western knowledge to see beyond its blinkers, to gain more understanding of itself and its own limitations.

Seeing beyond these blinkers might draw on the horizon-imagining experimentations of philosophical work. Here I would like to consider briefly the work of just two philosophers: Heidegger and Camus. These two are of particular relevance to an analysis of *Interstellar* because their questions concerning science come from an attention to an aesthetic that invites closer

attention to the poetic and, possibly, to love.

Camus, in *The Myth of Sisyphus*, speaks directly to science and a love for the world. He recognises that through science he might learn to settle upon certain truths of the quantum nature of things, but that the

science that was ready to teach me everything ends up in a hypothesis, that lucidity founders in metaphor, that uncertainty is resolved in a work of art. What need had I of so many efforts? The soft lines of these hills and the hand of evening on this troubled heart reach me much more. I have returned to my beginning. I realize that if through science I can seize phenomena and enumerate them, I cannot, for all that, apprehend the world. Were I to trace its entire relief with my finger, I should not know any more. (Camus, 1991, p. 20)

Camus offers this approach to an epistemological release through an attention to the beauty that is on the horizon. His troubled heart is massaged by his love for the world. His love for the world offers a sense of the horizons of a science that lacks a philosophical reflexivity (Stewart, 2022). Camus offers this sense through the release of poetry. Heidegger's concern for dwelling and measuring offers a similar release.

Through the poetry of Hölderlin, Heidegger (1971) wonders on poetry establishing a grounding, an earthing, that brings about dwelling. In *Building Dwelling Thinking*, Heidegger (1993a) continues on a path of questioning technology and human being. He questions what it means to, in particular, build and dwell, offering that “dwelling itself is always a staying with things” (Heidegger, 1993a, p. 353) and that learning to dwell is being in the world. Dwelling invokes a relationship of caring for, and of giving presence to (Heidegger, 1993a).

Heidegger's observation of the problem with thinking about measurement makes sense when considering Brand's problem. Heidegger (1971, p. 224) says:

When we hear of measure, we immediately think of number and imagine the two, measure and number, as quantitative. But the *nature* of measure is no more a quantum than is the *nature* of a number. True, we can reckon with numbers—but not with the nature of number. When Hölderlin envisages poetry as a measuring, and above all himself achieves poetry as taking measure ... we must pay heed to the kind of taking here, which does not consist in a clutching or any other kind of grasping, but rather in a letting come of what has been dealt out.

Through a questioning of measuring, Heidegger offers a recognition of the limits of science and of theorising that concerns Brand and that leads her to wonder about what might be offered in thinking about love. Love and poetry need not be seen as interchangeable here. Rather, love like poetry invites a different way of thinking through being and measuring that offers a way into thinking about dimensionality:

The upward glance passes aloft toward the sky, and yet it remains below on the earth. The upward glance spans the between of sky and earth. This between is measured out

for the dwelling of man. We now call the span thus meted out the dimension. This dimension does not arise from the fact that sky and earth are turned toward one another. Rather, their facing each other itself depends on the dimension. Nor is the dimension a stretch of space as ordinarily understood; for everything spatial, as something for which space is made, is already in need of the dimension, that is, that into which is it admitted. (Heidegger, 1971, p. 220)

A turn to love is here understood as a philosophical and educational turn, an opening up to love as educational in the sense of a deep connection to the world. As poetry might be seen to cause dwelling (Heidegger, 1971), perhaps then love can be seen to cause learning.

To play with this idea further, should children be studying love instead of studying calculus and physics at school? And might they discover the events beyond event horizons staying right here on Earth? Would a curriculum focused on love unlock the mysteries of time and gravity? Maybe, maybe not. What I'd like to propose is that this new curriculum would offer many other mysteries to explore, mysteries concerning care of the planet and everything on it, and caring for the horizons that disclose being.

Of course, one should be careful with sharing such innovations with policy makers in a Modern educational system. Suggesting that love should be a part of the curriculum could translate into an instrumental social conditioning, producing a series of normalised and enframing beliefs, ideas and practice, a measuring of the truths of love, and assessment of whether children meet the love grade. In other words, when Brand observes that maybe science needs to take more notice of love, whatever might be worth noticing could slip through anxiously clutching hands.

Camus' exploration of atoms and the horizon in *The Myth of Sisyphus* and Heidegger's work with dimensionality in "...*Poetically Man Dwells...*" might provide alternative readings on love and science for this curriculum. Heidegger's thinking might stretch dimensionality beyond the ordinary notions of measurement and bring new dimension to dimensions through a poetry of dwelling and measuring, an attention to the "breadth of being" (1971, p. 222). Curriculum-wise, this turn might look like a slowing down of the measuring events that happen in education systems to, in Heidegger's words, "pay heed" (p. 224) to measuring, a "concentrated perception, a gathered taking-in, that remains a listening" (p. 223).

However, in Aotearoa New Zealand, attention to Mātauranga Māori has already been recognised as a way to remove the 'blinkers' of science (Stewart, 2022) or perhaps even move beyond the horizon—that event horizon that Mann chauvinistically regards as rarely crossed. In working with the poetic measuring of dimensions, the nation already has many opportunities. For three very brief examples:

1. Rau and Ritchie (2011) engage the meaning of *whakapapa* as presencing intimate relationships with the Earth and with family, and revealing a different understanding of the temporality of these relationships.
2. Rameka speaks to "Māori perspectives of time ... the past, the present and the future are viewed as intertwined" (Rameka, 2016, p. 387). Life is "a continuous cosmic process"

(Rameka, 2016, p. 387); time is untethered, free from any sense of linearity or even perhaps inevitability. To think of the future as being behind requires thinking about one's position in relation to what is knowable and what can be seen. The experience of time is understood as having spiritual dimensions. Experiences of time are threads that intertwine with experiences of spirituality, family and community, genealogy and so on (Rameka, 2016).

3. Stewart's (2021b, p. 109) recognition of the concept of love in relation to the concept in *te reo Māori* (the Māori language) of *aroha* works with the recognition of love as "infinite." While stressing that the concepts of love and *aroha* are close, they don't "completely match" (Stewart, 2021b, p. 82), and the ways in which their horizons are distinct offers generative educational questions concerning the association of *aroha* with open-mindedness, generosity, and attentiveness, an infinite, "boundless sense of responsibility for the Other" (Stewart, 2021b, p. 83). *Aroha* then puts forth a challenge to Mann with regard just where that line of sight might really end.

While it would be dangerous to suggest Camus, or Heidegger, or *Interstellar's* cosmic flows between daughter and father are in any way analogous with a cosmic perspective of love and life, and the implications of this perspective for a science of event horizons, there is at the same time a resonance that invites wonder. Wondering about time in this way does have its traditional epistemological chauvinisms (Young, 2002) to detether. Allowing for the possibility that love transcends time is however not a new small step for 'man' nor a new giant leap for 'mankind' as humanity looks to reach the stars. Those steps and leaps are ancient to communities that have understood the essence of a relationship to the stars and horizons and events and time and dimensionality and love. The challenge of letting go of predominant understandings of the way in which time works is a challenge of letting go of many apparent Modern comforts and securities. To give up on time would be like giving up on the Internet—it's possibly inconceivable (or at least, the inability to believe in the possibility of an altogether different understanding of time is a very serious condition that defines a process of industrial normalisation and a colonising project that has tick-tocked around the world). If a certain technologically oriented forgetfulness is indeed a condition of Modernity (Heidegger, 1993b), forgetting alternative relationships to time might be one of the key devices for locking thinking into a predictable and inevitable flow that at the same time is the blinkering that denies an open perspective of the cosmos.

Conclusion: Working beyond the event horizon through love and early childhood care and education

This paper concludes with a turn to the context of early childhood care and education and horizons of love. Love and early childhood education sit in a particular relationship that might still make sense and that might offer the philosophy of education a space less hostile to an embracing of love and science. However, this conclusion also shows those philosophical dimensions and possibilities to be under new forms of educational policing through a renewal of very Modern educational traditions in behaviour management—traditions that might be evidence of an absence of love (Lanas and Zembylas, 2015), and that warrant questioning through a theory of love.

In early childhood care and education, an interest in the behavioural sciences fuels a tendency to

work with behaviour management as if it is pedagogy (Arndt, Gibbons, and Fitzsimons, 2015). How does this appear to us? Think of an educational space where all the available spaces on the walls are covered with star charts, loudly proclaiming which children are measuring up to the approved measures of good learning and good behaviour.

The education and care of the child before they reach school age, in many nations around the world, has become a central concern for government. This concern reflects a largely economy-driven realisation in the potential economic benefits of investment in, and regulation of, the child's early care and education experiences. Perhaps most notably, an elevated interest in the care and education of the child is evident in the OECD's comprehensive review of early childhood care and education research and policy—the 'Starting Strong' series (see for instance Barata, 2018). Before starting strong, however, there was an intensification of economic interest and economic thinking in the analysis of longitudinal data of the effects of early childhood care and education for some communities (see for instance Belfield, Nores, Barnett, and Schweinhart, 2006).

This highly technical and pseudo-scientific dimension of educational space might pay heed to measuring through an exploration of love. This exploration is not limited to an affective political operation (Lanas and Zembylas, 2015), but rather opens up to new modes of thinking power and an understanding of thinking as in some kind of interdimensional relationship with emotion, choice, politics and praxis (Lanas and Zembylas, 2015)—a gravity-shattering force and an approach to making sense of the cosmos beyond event horizons. Mann's lecture is an important moment with regard to what is in and out of sight, and the ways in which love might not resolve in the evolutionary ways that Mann understands. Mann cannot think beyond certain functionalities. Having theorised love as a basic behaviouristic survival instinct, Mann reveals he has insufficiently attended to love as a theoretically rich line of inquiry in its own right. Love is beyond Mann's questions and his horizon; he misunderstands what he has discovered about knowledge and being, and "allows the possibility of no other reality-revealing horizon" (Young, 2002, p. 29).

If Mann allows for the possibility that love transcends time and space, he discovers new questions. What might happen then if children and teachers question the whats and hows and whys of the reality-revealing horizon of behaviourism? Perhaps their questions would make these star charts seem somehow strange ... to wonder how those beautiful stars in the sky, that offer up ideas of unknowable life and death, that hint at dimensions of time and gravity beyond sight, became the crude instrument of a community's love for enframing the behaviour of children. I wonder whether then this love might also be revealed for its very Modern tendencies, and then put aside to grow dust, replaced with a different kind of less anxious, more questioning, more dimensional, more essential, love.

As an early childhood teacher and teacher educator in Aotearoa New Zealand, for me it's not just love that is of interest here, but the way in which love is thought differently through the partnership established in the signing of the aforementioned treaty, which consists of two treaties: the Treaty of Waitangi and te Titiri o Waitangi, two versions of an agreement in two languages with the purpose of coming together in partnership.

One place to look for that partnership is in the early childhood curriculum. It is perhaps getting

closer to the source of love. In Aotearoa New Zealand's early childhood curriculum *Te Whāriki* (Ministry of Education, 2017), love is a secondary concept to *aroha*. *Aroha* is explained as love, compassion, empathy and affection (p. 66). *Aroha* is a key curriculum concept with regard to the child's learning dispositions, relationship to *Papatūānuku* (typically explained as the Earth mother), and relationships with peers. The curriculum can be seen then as guiding *mahi aroha*, practices through which mana is recognised, protected, and enhanced (Cram, 2021), and invites thinking about the kind of measuring that compels Heidegger and Camus, and at the same time invites a concern for any sciences that anxiously attempt to fix education and childhood through blinkered approaches to measurement. Take for example this star chart phenomenon.

The managerial star chart is emblematic of events that have occurred in early childhood education over the two decades either side of the turn of the millennium and that obscure anxieties with regard to the enumeration of the child in ways that trouble this heart. When I started out teaching in early childhood education many years ago, the early childhood education sector had only just appeared on the educational radar of the Cold War. It was largely free to do whatever it wished with regard to providing for the care and education of children, and many children were not likely to spend much more than 20 hours a week in an early childhood centre.

Travelling through time, to early childhood education, here in Aotearoa New Zealand now, we have this seemingly paradoxical situation in which the Government maintains that early childhood education is not a compulsory educational stage, but at the same time compels parents to send their children to early childhood education centres at increasingly younger ages, for increasing hours in the week.

I am concerned with what is overlooked, discarded, marginalised, and exploited in this brave new world of early childhood education. I am particularly concerned with the incessant and absurd production of star charts and other tools to measure the young child's educational progress. For instance, we are currently, in Aotearoa New Zealand, being asked to implement a host of new "progress tools" to amplify the attention to evidence of each child's learning and development. We must measure the children more.

I read in Heidegger, Camus, and *Interstellar* a challenge to education systems obsessed with the metric production of educational quantities. The enumeration of each child, and of all children, educationally, appears to be an absurd obsession, fixated with producing numbers and rarely, in Heidegger's terms, paying heed to those productions, nor to the nature of number (Heidegger, 1971, p. 224). I am wondering whether a fixation of enumerating the child might be challenged not just through a turn to Heidegger but also a turn to the kind of hard science fiction that questions the truths of the educational sciences, and that opens up questions concerning events, horizons, education and love.

A love-oriented curriculum can be understood in different ways.

Of course, there's the possibility that love becomes some kind of truth, or a prescribed lesson, and something to assess. Perhaps the main caution here is to think of love as a phenomenon worth more study. To study love is not to determine its finality. The point is not to harass love until it's a thing that can be put to work for some agenda, but to dwell poetically in love (Heidegger, 1971).

Perhaps in dwelling poetically in the study of love there is some recognition of the very tendency to turn love into a potion for “gain and success” (Heidegger, 1971, p. 213). In other words, an education reform movement that seeks to install love into curriculum as a subject area, or into pedagogy as a teaching tool, could end up looking and feeling just as absurd as every other instrumental and technical curriculum subject and pedagogy, a reform that might rarely extend beyond our line of sight.

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